

NATURAL FIBER-GYPSUM MATRIX COMPOSITES. ANALYSIS OF CRITICAL LENGTH.

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ABSTRACT

In previous work¹, the modulus of rupture and toughness increase of Sisal Short Fiber Reinforced Hemihydrated Gypsum has been analyzed. The sisal critical length was obtained on theoretical ground. In this communication an experimental assessment of sisal critical length in gypsum matrix is presented. It is based on laboratory tests of fiber debonding and pull-out, controlling the water/gypsum ratio and the matrix porosity as the main characteristics of the matrix material. Finally, a discussion is included relating these results with the previously obtained on theoretical grounds after three points bending tests of prismatic gypsum reinforced samples.

1. INTRODUCTION

Hemihydrated gypsum ($\text{CaSO}_4 \cdot 1/2\text{H}_2\text{O}$) is a well known building material. After setting, gypsum plaster is brittle, non resistant and mainly used for finishing. Sisal is a cheap natural fiber, compatible with gypsum matrix and easily available in a lot of countries, not only tropical ones. The composite Sisal short fiber reinforced Gypsum (SG) exhibit a better mechanical performance than Gypsum matrix alone.

Critical length is an important property of short fiber reinforcing materials¹. It is directly related with adherence between brittle matrix and fiber surface, in such a way that to determine the critical length from laboratory tests, experiments on fiber-matrix adherence may be designed. The adherence between gypsum matrix and fibers been a general result of plaster hardening and close interpenetrating of gypsum as it is expanding during setting and introducing into fiber surface roughness, creating radial compressive stresses over the fibers too.

Nevertheless, sisal fibers absorb water from hydrated gypsum during the first stage of setting, with volume increase. In a second stage, the water absorption is reverted to water desorption, with volume decreasing. This cycle can damage the fiber-matrix adherence performance.

2. OBJECTIVES

The main objectives of this work has been to obtain experimentally the critical length of sisal fibers in gypsum matrix, manufactured with different water/gypsum ratios and to analyze gypsum porosity influence on fiber/matrix adherence. A display of one experimental arrangement is collected in fig. 1.

Fig. 1. Adherence test (scheme)

According to simple analysis, the fiber breaking length L inside the gypsum matrix can be obtained by the expression

$$L = \frac{d\sigma_f}{4\tau_{fm}} \quad (1)$$

where, d is the fiber diameter, σ_f fiber tensile strength and τ_{fm} fiber-matrix interface shear strength, experimentally obtained in laboratory tests for several water/gypsum ratios.

3. MATERIALS

The matrix material is Hemihydrated gypsum after setting, with nominal flexural strength 3,5 MPa in three points bending test (water/gypsum ratio = 0,8). The Sisal fiber from Venezuela has the following characteristics, after laboratory tests: 0,9 -1,2 m length, mean diameter 0,19 mm, water absorption 64,2%, moisture content 4,9%; tensile strength 127,5 MPa; ductility 2,6%; elastic modulus 5,5 GPa.

Fibers have a rugged surface, allowing good fiber-matrix adherence during set of gypsum matrix.

4. EXPERIMENTS

Two kinds of experiments have been conducted, here designed I and II.

4.1. Tests I

Several batches of prismatic gypsum samples have been manufactured (specimens size 40x40x160 mm). At the very beginning of gypsum set, one fiber of sisal is partly embedded centered in each specimen, being free the other long extreme of the fiber. Specimens are then drying in laboratory (20 ± 2 °C and 65 ± 5 % relative humidity).

Fibers debonding have been accomplished pulling the free fiber extreme, in fiber direction, under a load rate of 0,2 N/s, with an universal Instron machine (Institute E. Torroja, Madrid), until fiber rupture or debonding and pull-out (fig. 1).

Table 1 collects experimental results of fibers extraction tests, modifying embedded fiber length, water/gypsum ratio, tensile and shear stress. Fig. 2 displays the linear relation appearing between embedded fiber length and tensile debonding stress for constant water/gypsum ratio of matrix material. There are similar relations for different w/g values, but the slope decreases as w/g ratio increases.

Table 1. Experimental results of fiber extraction tests type I.

Batch	Water/gypsum ratio (w/g)	Fiber length (mm)	Fiber tensile stress (MPa)	Fiber-matrix shear stress (MPa)	Fiber-matrix shear stress (MPa). Constant w/g ratio
1	0,5	20	69	0,17	0,17
2	0,6	10	24	0,15	0,15
3	0,6	20	44	0,10	
4	0,6	30	72	0,16	
5	0,6	40	91	0,15	
6	0,7	20	46	0,08	
7	0,7	40	60	0,07	0,06
8	0,8	20	20	0,06	
9	0,8	40	26	0,05	
10	0,9	40	25	0,04	
11	1,0	20	20	0,04	0,04
12	1,0	40	25	0,03	

Fig. 2.- Relation between embedded fiber length and tensile debonding stress for constant water/gypsum ratio of matrix material.

Fiber-matrix shear stresses are included in Table 1 for fiber extraction tests. It can be seen that a characteristic value (mean value) there exists for constant water/gypsum ratio, that is, for characteristic value of the matrix porosity. Fig. 3 contains the quadratic relation experimentally obtained from these laboratory tests, between w/g (or porosity) and fiber-matrix shear strength.

From eq. (1), critical fiber length can be calculated for matrix materials with different porosity, assuming a constant value of fiber tensile stress (130 MPa) and fiber diameter (0,19 mm).

Fig. 3.- Fiber-matrix shear stress vs. water/gypsum ratio.

In fig. 4 a graphical representation of fiber critical length (mm) in function of the w/g ratio (inverse to porosity) is included.

Fig. 4.- Fiber critical length vs. water/gypsum ratio.

4.2. Tests II

Fig. 5 displays experimental arrangement of test II. Cylindrical specimens of gypsum contain sisal fibers, as that figure shows. Increasing load is applied to fiber until fiber debonding and pull-out.

Four series of specimens have been manufactured. All cylindrical, with a sisal fiber axially inside gypsum samples. Each series consists of three specimens, in laboratory dried.

Fig. 5.- Experimental scheme for adherence tests II.

Table 2 collects experimental results of four specimens series tested, where w/g ratio has been changed from 0,5 to 0,8. In all except two cases ($w/g=0,5$), fibers were extracted from gypsum matrix at loads in table 2 included as fiber tensile stress (MPa), obtained dividing extraction load by fiber section. Shear strength has been obtained from eq. 1, with σ instead σ_f , and L being fiber length inside gypsum matrix.

Table 2. Adherence tests II experimental results.

Batch	Water/gypsum ratio	Fiber tensile stress (MPa)	Fiber-matrix shear strength (MPa)
1	0,5	167	0,19
2	0,6	122	0,16
3	0,7	63	0,08
4	0,8	43	0,07

Fig. 6 displays relation between w/g ratio in gypsum manufacturing and fiber-matrix shear strength. There appears a close parabolic equation which can be related with porosity through some exponential decreasing shear strength as w/g ratio increases, that is, as gypsum porosity increases.

In fig. 7 fiber critical lengths in Type I and Type II laboratory tests are collected, in function of water/gypsum ratio (inverse of specimens porosity). As it can be seen, for low w/g values, the fiber critical length is not matrix porosity or test type sensitive. Nevertheless, at high w/g values, fiber critical length is both, test type and matrix porosity sensitive.

Fig. 6. Experimental relation between w/g ratio and fiber-matrix shear strength.

Fig. 7.- Fiber critical length vs. Water/gypsum ratio (Type I and Type II)

5. CONCLUSIONS

Short fibers reinforcing materials have a characteristic critical length, mainly dependent on fiber diameter, fiber tensile strength and fiber-matrix shear strength. It has been shown possible to obtain the critical length of short Sisal fibers embedded in gypsum matrix, appearing very sensitive to matrix porosity through water/gypsum ratio in gypsum manufacturing process. The fiber critical length has been calculated after measuring fiber-matrix strength in laboratory fiber debonding test.

References

- 1 F. Hernández-Olivares, I. Oteiza and L. de Villanueva. "Experimental analysis of toughness and modulus of rupture increase of sisal short fiber reinforced hemihydrated gypsum". Composites Structures. Vol. 22, 1992. 123-137.